

POTENTIAL APPLICATION OF WIRE WOVEN MESH AS TOWER PACKING SUPPORT

COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Wire woven metals are new type of truss-like periodic cellular metals (PCM) that have several applications ranging from different loading applications to filtering processes. Their lightness, decent structural integrity and other thermo-fluid mechanics have resulted in a multi-functional structure. Wire bulk cross (WBC), that is a truss-like PCM, is recently found to be the premier truss-like cellular metals with extraordinary mechanical behaviours. Some of these unique behaviours are normalized compressive, shear strength and resistance to buckling effects. In terms of fluid dynamics homogeneity of these structures can also provide a uniform flow with minimal pressure drop and velocity perturbation for industries that maintaining design and operating conditions of flow is critical.

In this research, 2D representative of wire bulk cross (WBC) and textile core are modelled for 10 different aperture sizes. Mechanical and fluid behaviour of the 2D model and vapor flow are then predicted when aperture size changed with constant small increments. In Oil & Gas industry, packing towers imply an essential condition that operating conditions of vapor flows should remain unchanged, while heavy random packings, mounted on the top, are well-supported. Thus, investigation on effects of wire woven mesh screen aperture size on its structural integrity, while minimising flow pressure-drop and velocity profile changes can introduce these truss-like structures as tower packing supports in future.

In this research, using FEA, wire woven screens undergo several aperture sizes to investigate the mechanical behaviour of the structure. Similarly, CFD analysis conducted to simulate the behaviour of vapor flows through these wire woven mesh screens. The numerical results are then plotted against both porosity ratio and aperture size to indicate the mechanical and flow behaviour patterns. In the CFD analysis graphs, flooding point of the nominated N_2 flow is shown to give an inside into the points when flow might enter flooded region. Results showed deflection of the mesh under the load, fluid velocity profile and pressure drop values level off after certain sizes are reached. Normalized combination of these analysis are plotted to be used to find an optimised size range (using Simplex Optimisation Method-graphical solution) that meet the requirements in specific industry applications.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

- **FEA:** Finite element analysis for all the cases conducted using SolidWorks for geometrical modelling and Ansys Workbench (Mechanical) for stress analysis.
- The Steel SUS-304 with the mechanical properties mentioned in the Table below is used for the FEA analysis.

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Tensile Yield Strength (MPa)	Poisson Ratio
STEEL SUS 304	200	7850	250	0.30

- Based on the current Oil & Gas tower design principles, aperture sizes are selected based on maximum size of commonly used C-Ring random packing, which is 75 mm, for larger packing towers to 20 mm, for smaller diameter towers.

Column Diameter (m)	Use Packing Size (mm (in))
< 0.3 m (1 ft)	25 mm (1 in.)
0.3 to 0.9 m (1 to 3 ft)	25 to 38 mm (1 to 1.5 in.)
> 0.9 m	50 to 75 mm (2 to 3 in.)

- **CFD:** Computational fluid dynamics for the models is done by Ansys Workbench (Fluent). N_2 vapor as common gas mixture in distillation and absorption tower with 1.06 m/s flowed through the wire woven mesh screen. Reynold number, Re_s , that is for screen, approximately ranged from 400-700 while Re_d , that is based on wire diameter and freestream velocity was almost 400.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CONCLUSION

- The combined and normalized diagrams can give an optimized porosity ratio ranges, $\frac{d}{L}$, during the design of the recommended WBC and textile core metal matrixes, or any other truss-like PCMs. These diagrams are very helpful when both fluid characteristics and structural integrity of any specific type of truss-like PCM is of importance.
- The optimum design condition fell in the middle section of normalized graphs, and between the intersection of normalized fluid dynamics and solid mechanics graphs.
- By simplex optimization method (graphical solution), all these intersection points can be evaluated based on the significance of the different factors in each project.
- The results indicate the behavior of both fluid characteristics and solid mechanics tend to be opposite each other and level off after a certain aperture size is reached.

